

POSSIBILITIES OF USING THE DESI INTEGRAL INDEX IN ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LEGUMINOUS CROPS

Gabbarov Sabit Nietalievich

Associate Professor, Karakalpak State University

gabbarovs@mail.ru

Xudaybergenov Mirsayd Karimbergenovich

Independent Researcher, Karakalpak State University

xmirsayd@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18997978>

Abstract: This thesis analyzes the scientific and methodological foundations for the comprehensive assessment of the efficiency of legume crop production. The study proposes the **DESI (Legume Efficiency Composite Index)**, which integrates several efficiency indicators into a single composite measure. The research results make it possible to objectively assess efficiency by taking agroecological conditions into account, compare results across regions, and provide a scientific basis for the development of sustainable agricultural policy.

Keywords: legume crops, agricultural economics, DESI index, nitrogen balance index, intercropping efficiency, agroecological efficiency, adjustment coefficient.

The production system of legume grain crops constitutes an important component of the agricultural sector. It plays a decisive role not only in ensuring food security but also in restoring and stabilizing soil fertility. Therefore, a thorough scientific analysis of the economic efficiency indicators in the cultivation of these crops is among the most pressing issues of today. Evaluating the state of agro-resource utilization — particularly assessing efficiency for proper cost management — is of critical importance and establishes clear directions for the development of this sector.

By conducting an in-depth study of the scientific and theoretical foundations for the "Legume Crop Efficiency Index (DESI – Legume Efficiency Composite Index)", it is possible to develop this index while taking into account the Nitrogen Balance Index (NBI) and the Intercrop Efficiency Index (ICI).

If we consider the essence of the Legume Crop Efficiency Index (DESI), it represents an integral indicator that comprehensively evaluates the contribution of nitrogen fixation by legume crops, the efficiency of intercropping, and economic profitability. Its general form is as follows:

$$DESI = w_1 \times NBI + w_2 \times ICI + w_3 \times EEI$$

where w_1 , w_2 , w_3 are the weighting coefficients of each sub-index; NBI stands for the Nitrogen Balance Index, ICI for the Intercrop Efficiency Index, and EEI for the Economic Efficiency Index.

The Nitrogen Balance Index (NBI – Nitrogen Balance Index) accounts for the nitrogen cycle in the soil and the share of biological nitrogen fixed by legume crops. The formula for this index takes the following form.

In the conditions of Karakalpakstan, dividing the territories into irrigated and drought-prone categories when assessing the efficiency of legume grain crops is both scientifically and practically justified. In this context, it is advisable to introduce adjustment (correction) coefficients by district when calculating the Legume Crop Efficiency Index (DESI). These

coefficients take into consideration the climatic conditions, the level of water supply, and the natural variations in soil fertility.

The districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are divided into two groups, for each of which recommended adjustment coefficients can be proposed (Table 1).

Table 1.

Establishment of regional correction coefficients when assessing the effectiveness of leguminous crops in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (based on the DESI index)

Group	Districts	Correction Coefficient (author's recommendation) (k_i)	Explanation
Irrigated territories	Nukus, Khojeyli, Takhtakupyr, Chimbay, Kanlykul, Amudarya	0,9	Water supply is stable, intensive technologies are used. The state of $DESI \geq 0.65$ is assessed as high efficiency.
Areas prone to drought	Kungrad, Muynak, Shumanay, Karauzyak, Turtkul, Beruni	0.7	Water resources are limited, the climate is arid. The $DESI \geq 0.45$ state is assessed as high efficiency.
Correction formula	$DESI_{corrected} = DESI \times k_i$		Indexation method, taking into account the influence of natural conditions for each district.

In this method, the DESI index is first determined as a general (overall) indicator (for example, based on yield, nutritional value, and economic efficiency). Subsequently, the real situation is expressed by applying an adjustment coefficient that corresponds to the agroecological conditions of each district.

For example, if the calculated DESI in Takhtakupir district equals 0.68, and the district belongs to the irrigated areas category with an accepted correction coefficient $k_i = 0.95$, the adjusted value is calculated as:

$$DESI_{corr} = 0.68 \times 0.95 = 0.65.$$

In this way, the analysis results are brought closer to actual conditions, and regional differences are evaluated on a solid scientific basis.

It should be emphasized that integral indicators comprising economic, social, and ecological parameters are of fundamental and decisive importance in the scientific assessment of legume grain crop efficiency. These indicators make it possible to evaluate not only yield or economic profit, but also resource-saving efficiency, labor productivity, and the level of agroecological sustainability. The comprehensive application of such indicators creates an opportunity to assess social benefits and the state of natural resources alongside economic outcomes in agricultural sectors.

The Legume Crop Efficiency Index (DESI) developed in this scientific study is a multi-factor evaluation method that serves as an objective criterion integrating economic profitability, agroecological efficiency, and technological sustainability. The index incorporates indicators such as soil fertility preservation, nitrogen balance, and intercropping effectiveness, with their relative weights determined on the basis of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) or normalization methods. A scale of DESI values has been developed, enabling a scientifically grounded classification of efficiency levels (low, medium, high). This scale allows comparison of research results across districts, identification of the most effective agrosystems, and formulation of practical recommendations.

As a result, even in regions with harsh climatic conditions such as Karakalpakstan, it becomes possible to conduct a fair and accurate assessment of efficiency. This approach represents a modern and adaptive scientific method for determining legume crop efficiency and serves as an important methodological foundation for shaping sustainable agricultural policy and scientifically substantiating regional development strategies.

Conclusion. The Legume Crop Efficiency Index (DESI) developed in the scientific study has acquired significant importance as an integral indicator for evaluating agrosystem efficiency on the basis of economic, ecological, and technological criteria. The inclusion of factors such as soil fertility preservation, nutrient element balance, and intercropping effectiveness in the index composition has ensured the objectivity of the evaluation process. The DESI scale has enabled precise classification of efficiency levels and comparison of results across districts. At the same time, the application of adjustment coefficients that take into account differences in climate and irrigation resources has brought the results closer to real agroecological conditions. This approach has become of major methodological importance in the formation of sustainable agricultural policy and the scientific substantiation of regional development strategies.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Исомиддинов И.Т., Рахмонов Ж.Х., Мамбетназаров А.Б., Сатторов Ш. Турли мавсумларда экиладиган дуккакли дон экинларининг касаллик ва бегона ўтларига қарши кураш чоралари тавсиянома. Ўсимликларни ҳимоя қилиш ИТИ. “MNA-SHON” Тошкент-2020.
2. Umarov S.R., Qudratov A.A. Dukkakli don ekinlarining mamlakatimiz qishloq xo‘jaligidagi iqtisodiy ahamiyati va samaradorligi // “Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va tahlil” ilmiy elektron jurnal. - Toshkent, 2024. - № 4 (20). - Б. 192-197.
3. Фарманов Т.Х. Дуккакли дон маҳсулотларини етиштириш, сақлаш, қайта ишлаш ва бошқа жараёнларида қўшилган қиймат занжирини ривожлантириш/“Ўзбекистонда биоиктисодиётга оид биоресурсларни барқарор бошқариш бўйича билимлар, тадқиқотлар ва илғор тажрибалар” мавзусидаги иккинчи халқаро биоиктисодиёт форумининг материаллари. – Тошкент: ТДАУ, 2023й.- 417 бет.
4. Холиқов Б., Иминов А. Ғалладан бўшаган майдонларда мош етиштириш // “Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги” журнали, 2016. -№6. – Б. 6.
5. Худайкулов Ж.Б., Аманова М.Э. Яшил нўхат ва ясмиқ етиштириш [Матн] : 100 китоб тўплами, 28-китоб, илмий нашр / «Агробанк» АТБ.-Тошкент: "ТАСВИР" нашриёт уйи, 2021. -40 б.